

HYPERVELOCITY IMPACT DAMAGE IN CARBON-CARBON
AND CARBON-EPOXY COMPOSITES
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ABSTRACT

A high irradiance single beam short pulsed Nd: glass laser was used to generate shock waves in carbon-carbon and carbon epoxy composites. Dynamic brittle fracture at hypervelocity impact conditions was observed as a result of reflected shock waves as tensile waves from the back surface of samples. Successive stages of damage from incipient spallation to complete sample perforation were obtained by increasing gradually the laser energy. The thermo-mechanical damage on the front surface as a result of laser interaction with the target material, and the mechanical damage at the back surface as a result of shock wave reflection were characterized by optical and scanning electron microscopy. The failure properties of the carbon composites were related to the processing of densification and graphitization mode. While the failure properties for carbon epoxy composites were related to impact direction versus fiber direction. A comparison was made between spall properties of carbon epoxy composites with aluminum and iron.

A new experimental method was developed to calculate the attenuation of laser generated shock waves. This technique enables also the evaluation of the laser induced spall pressure in different materials.

KEYWORDS: Laser induced shock waves, Dynamic response, Hypervelocity impact, Carbon/Carbon, Carbon epoxy.

1. INTRODUCTION

Shock loads can be generated by high speed impact, explosives or by intense short time energy deposition. While in most impact experiments the impact time is in the microsecond time scale, the laser impact time is in the nanosecond regime. It is important to know the stages of material failure, in particular the conditions of incipient damage and the pressure responsible for this damage as well as the pressure attenuation in the sample for shock loading.

Some composites such as carbon-carbon are used for components which should withstand high temperatures as well as impacts. Carbon-epoxy composites are replacing high performance metal parts in space components due to their high strength to weight ratio.

Experimental work has been performed to establish the ablative characteristics of some composites using continuous wave CO₂ laser (1-3). There is however no published work on the impact behaviour of composites

using short pulsed laser. To our knowledge we are the first to investigate this subject.

Our work is based on our previous experience on spall and dynamic fracture in metals (4-8) using laser induced shock waves. The advantage of our method as compared to other impact experiments is the study of thermomechanical damage at strain rates of the order of 10^7 sec^{-1} , corresponding to hypervelocity impact conditions.

In laser-matter interaction the heated material is blown off as plasma and the ablation drives a shock wave into the target. At the final stages of the laser pulse, the ablation pressure at the surface drops and a rarefaction wave propagates into the target, following the shock wave. This pressure wave has approximately a triangular shape; after reaching the back surface of the target it is reflected as a tension (negative pressure). Dynamic fracture and spall is a result of very short tensile stresses exceeding the dynamic strength of the material. Spall pressure is impact time dependent, and for very short transient times a reasonable prediction of dynamic spall strength (pressure) is needed.

The values of ablation induced shock pressure can be calculated by sophisticated hydrodynamic simulation codes. However, to a good approximation an analytic quantitative estimate of the ablation pressure is given by the following formula (9).

$$P_{kb} = 230 A^{7/6} Z^{-9/16} \lambda^{-1/4} \tau^{-1/8} \left[\frac{I}{10^{12}} \right]^{3/4} \quad (1)$$

where, the pressure is given in kilobars, A is the atomic weight, Z the ionization number, λ the laser wavelength in μm , τ the laser pulse time in nanoseconds and I is the laser intensity in W/cm^2 .

Diagnostics of high pressures in the range of kbars-Mbars on a nanosecond time scale is still a challenge, therefore calculations of these effects are achieved by large laser-matter hydrodynamic codes. These codes require a full understanding on many parameters and are therefore a major effort.

A new approach is presented here to estimate experimentally the spall stress and the pressure gradient in different materials using the effect of spall in targets by laser induced shock waves. At threshold spall, we have the same spall pressure (stress) and the same shock velocity at the rear surface for different target thicknesses. Using targets with decreasing thicknesses, the laser induced plasma ablation pressure P, represents the real spall stress (P_s) and a value corresponding to pressure dispersion through the target thickness ΔX .

$$P = P_s + \frac{P}{X} \Delta X + \dots \quad (2)$$

By extrapolating the experimental values for zero thickness $\Delta X = 0$, the limiting value will represent the dynamic spall pressure. For small values of ΔX the Taylor expansion can be approximated by the first two terms given in eq. 2. In this case the slope will represent the pressure gradient. Experiments were performed to evaluate the pressure decay and spall pressure for isotropic and anisotropic materials using laser induced shock waves.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

A high irradiance ($10^{10} - 10^{13}$ W/cm²) single beam pulsed Nd:glass laser was used to generate shock waves in composites. We used a modified Gaussian laser pulse with 3.5 nsec full width at half maximum intensity level (FWHM). Different energy levels were applied to determine stages of material failure from incipient to total perforation (burn through) of the sample, by a similar procedure used by us to study spallation and dynamic fracture in metals at ultra high strain rate (4-8).

Scanning electron microscopy was used to evaluate some characteristic damage stages on the surface or in sectioned samples.

The unidirectional carbon fiber (CF) epoxy composite specimens were prepared (10) from filament tows soaked with epoxy and stretched along the axis of a mold. The epoxy was prepared by mixing preheated Tonox 60/40 and DER-330, with RD-2 as diluter at 60°C. The pressed mold was subjected to two curing steps: 3 h at 80°C and one h at 140°C. The mold was cooled to room temperature and then unassembled. The fiber content of the composites was 60±2%. Several composite sample thicknesses were prepared from 0.2, to 2 mm.

Two impact directions were used for CF/epoxy composite: parallel and perpendicular to fiber directions.

Bidirectionally reinforced (2D) carbon-carbon composites were prepared from Xexcel 4C1008, 8 Harness, satin weaving carbon fabric reinforcement (Hexcel, California) by carbonization, graphitization and densification (11). After curing at 160°C and 1000 psi the material was carbonized at 1000°C, at atmospheric pressure in inert gas flow. This material was defined as "original" and is denoted by "O" in Table 1. The graphitization (G) is performed at 2600°C for 8 hours at atmospheric pressure in an inert gas.

The densification was performed by impregnation with coal-tar pitch.

(a) One densification cycle by pitch impregnation at low pressure and carbonization in a Hot-Isostatic Press (H) at 100 atm, and 650°C. This material is denoted by 1(H + G) in Table 1.

(b) Four densification cycles at atmospheric pressure (A) by dipping in molten pitch and carbonization in inert atmosphere at normal pressure at 1000°C. This material is denoted 4(A + G) in Table 1. Densities obtained by the two methods were almost identical.

Sample thicknesses for laser experiments were reduced to 0.55 mm by diamond saw cutting and polishing. The direction of cutting is parallel to the reinforcement, as can be seen also by the scanning electron micrographs.

Table 1. C/C composites and their properties

Samples	Flexural Strength (Kb) ASTM, D-790	Interlaminar Shear	
		Strength (kb) ASTM, D-2344	Bulk Density (gr/cc)
(O + G)	0.48 + 0.1	0.057	1.280
4(A + G)	0.68 ± 0.1	0.075	1.419
1(H + G)	1.20 ± 0.1	0.22	1.416

3. RESULTS

3.1 Damage in Carbon Epoxy Unidirectional Composites

Brittle fracture mode of the composites were observed at very low energy densities. However, the fracture was localized at the spall zone, and no internal delaminations or crack propagation were observed through the sample as an effect of shock wave propagation for impacts perpendicular to fiber direction. When impacts were along the fiber direction, the cracks propagated through the sample because the fibers did not act as crack arresters. No crack branching was observed on the sectioned samples.

The intensive heat pulse ablated the matrix on the front as a shallow crater while tensile (spall) fracture without heating was evident at the back surface. The mild damage on the front (laser side) correspond to severe spall damage on the back side, see figures 1 and 2, for a perpendicular impact. It is interesting to remark that incipient damage occurs at a relatively low energy density (195 J/cm^2 for a 0.5 mm sample), however, penetration of the sample was not achieved at 1500 J/cm^2 for one dimension shock wave condition (laser spot diameter of 2 mm for a 0.5 mm sample thickness). Also penetration of the carbon epoxy sample was not obtained for a focused beam of 50 KJ/cm^2 .

The unidirectional composite is stronger along the fiber direction than in the perpendicular direction.

The threshold pressure necessary to obtain incipient spallation of the samples was calculated from the plasma ablation pressure using the eq. 1.

A comparison was made between the impact behaviour at ultra high strain rate of CF/epoxy, aluminum and iron in order to evaluate their relative strength for short pulsed laser induced shock waves (10).

Fig. 1. Front surface damage at 1470 J/cm^2 in CF/epoxy.

Fig. 2. Fracture development at back surface at 515 J/cm^2 in CF/epoxy.

A linear dependence was obtained experimentally for the pressure as a function of target thickness, see fig. 3. The dynamic spall pressure for very short impacts was obtained by extrapolating the threshold values for zero target thickness to eliminate the contribution of the pressure dispersion. The following values were obtained: aluminum $26 \pm 2 \text{ Kbar}$, iron $57 \pm 5 \text{ kbar}$, carbon/epoxy composite (perpendicular to fiber direction) is $0.3 \pm 0.2 \text{ Kb}$ and 7 ± 0.5 for impact parallel to the fiber direction (12).

Our experiments yield directly the pressure gradient values (see fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Threshold plasma ablation for spall as a function of target thickness

The following values were obtained: aluminum has 57 ± 6 Kb/mm, iron has 154 ± 15 Kb/mm, for carbon fiber/epoxy composite it is 16 ± 2 Kb/mm when the impact is perpendicular to the fiber direction and 103 ± 20 Kb/mm when the impact is parallel (or along) the fiber direction. The large difference between the pressure gradient for perpendicular or parallel impact in unidirectional CF/epoxy is an experimental confirmation that the dispersion of the shock wave is significantly higher in the parallel direction. These results emphasize the tensor characteristics of anisotropic materials.

3.2 Damage in 2D Carbon-Carbon Composites

The two-dimensional (2D) samples used to compare their structural properties to thermo-mechanical damage by pulsed laser induced shock waves are summarized in Table 1.

Successive stages of damage in carbon-carbon composites were obtained by gradually increasing the laser energy. Densification by hot isostatic press provided a better perforation resistance material as compared to material densified at atmospheric pressure. The dynamic tensile strengths for 4(A + G) and 1(H + G) are comparable. Their strengths are larger by about a factor of 3 than that of (O + G) (11).

Sample perforation is scaling with energy density. As it can be seen from Table 2, there are considerable differences in perforation energy density as a result of densification and densification mode. No penetration (burn through) was obtained for sample 1(H + G) for the range of energy densities used in our experiments.

Table 2. Threshold and perforation energy densities of C/C composites for target thickness of 0.55 mm.

Sample	Threshold J/cm^2	Perforation J/cm^2
O + G	65 ± 20	1450 ± 300
4(A + G)	190 ± 30	5950 ± 300
1(H + G)	160 ± 30	8650

In figure 4 we can see the very shallow front (laser side) damage for $2800 J/cm^2$ due to ablation as compared to more extensive damage at the back due to spall at $800 J/cm^2$ (fig. 5).

Fig. 4. Sample 4(A + B), spallation at $800 J/cm^2$ in C/C composite.

Fig. 5. Front surface damage for $1(H + G)$ 2800 J/cm^2 in C/C composite.

4. CONCLUSIONS

A new experimental method was described to estimate the pressure gradient for laser induced shock waves in thin slab targets. The following values were obtained: aluminum has $57 \pm 6 \text{ Kb/mm}$, iron has $154 \pm 15 \text{ Kb/mm}$, for carbon fiber/epoxy composite it is $16 \pm 2 \text{ Kb/mm}$ when the impact is perpendicular to the fiber direction and $103 \pm 10 \text{ Kb/mm}$ when the impact is parallel (or along) the fiber direction. The large difference between the pressure gradient for perpendicular or parallel impact in unidirectional CF/epoxy is an experimental confirmation that the dispersion of the shock wave is significantly higher in the parallel direction. These results emphasize the tensor characteristics of anisotropic materials.

The dynamic spall pressure for very short impacts was obtained by extrapolating the threshold values for zero target thickness to eliminate the contribution of the pressure dispersion. The following values were obtained: aluminum $26 \pm 2 \text{ Kbar}$, iron $57 \pm 5 \text{ kbar}$, carbon/epoxy composite (perpendicular to fiber direction) is $0.3 \pm 0.2 \text{ Kb}$ and 7 ± 0.5 for impact parallel to the fiber direction.

The damage development in different carbon based composites was presented. Fracture morphologies emphasized the differences between front (ablation) or back (tensile) fracture modes. Densification of carbon-carbon composites by hot isostatic press provided a better penetration resistance material as compared to material densified at atmospheric pressure.

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